

Fig S1

TEM analysis images of the exosome counts for each group, N-Exos after sonication and H-Exo-Cur after sonication. TEM image scale bar : 100 nm.

Fig S2

HepG2 cell morphology treated with or without 500 μM of CoCl_2 . Shrunken morphologies and apoptotic bodies from hypoxic HepG2 cells were observed. Microscopy image scale bar : 100 μm

Fig S3

Uptake of dye-labeled exosomes into HepG2 cells monitored by confocal laser scanning microscopy. Cell nuclei were labeled with DAPI (blue) signals, and exosomal membranes were labeled with common exosome marker TSG101-FITC (green) signals. Successfully uptake induced by ultrasound was observed. Confocal microscopy image scale bar : 10 μ m.